

ECONOMICS

ECONOMIC GROWTH OF RA AND THE ROLE OF PUBLIC EXPENDITURES IN IT

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Abstract

Economic growth around the world is a key objective for the government of a country and identifying the drivers of economic growth is important for policymakers who seek sustainable economic growth through prudent fiscal policies. In the article, a study of the dynamics of RA economic growth was carried out, comparisons were made between the indicators of other countries. Then economic growth was studied from the perspectives of supply and demand, and the main factors contributing to economic growth were pointed out. After that, the dynamics and structure of state expenditures were addressed, and the correlation between economic growth and budget expenditures and contribution of expenditures in economic growth was presented. At the end of the article, the main conclusions and proposals are briefly presented.

Keywords: economic growth, public expenditure, drivers of economic growth, correlation.

Economic growth refers to an increase in the productive capacity of an economy, whereby the economy is able to produce additional quantities of goods and services. Ensuring stable rates of economic growth creates favorable conditions for reducing the level of poverty in the country, raising the living standard of the

population, expanding the scope of activities of economic entities, and developing infrastructure. During the twenty-year period, global economic growth had a tendency to slow down, and the COVID-19 pandemic led to a deep recession of the global economy of 3.0%, about 1.7 percent exceeding the effects of the financial and economic crisis of 2008.

Graph 1. The dynamics of economic growth in Armenia and the world Source: World Bank

In 2020, under the conditions of the coronavirus pandemic and the shocks of the Artsakh war, the economic decline of Armenia amounted to 7.4%, unlike the global index, the decline recorded in Armenia during the financial and economic crisis of 2008 was deeper. Surprisingly, against the background of slowing economic growth in the world economy and the economies of Armenia's main partner countries, in 2022, RA stood out with a fairly high economic growth of 12.6%. It is clear that differences in economic growth among countries around the world are significant, and equally significant are the disparities in post-crisis economic recovery, thus leading to sharp increases in inequality within and across countries. Here

the question arises, what is the reason for the fluctuation of economic growth, what is the reason that the consequences of the crisis are big in one country, less in another country, and what is the result that different countries recover from the post-crisis situation at different speed and extent? Thus, the purpose of the research is to identify the factors on account of which the economic growth of RA was recorded, at the same time, in order to respond to crisis situations with an effective policy, it is important to identify the role of government spending in the economic growth of RA. Both the amount of budget expenditures and their distribution have an impact on economic growth. Budget allocation

choices can either accelerate economic growth or hinder its progress. In this article, we have studied the structure of RA economic growth and budget expenditures, the various components contributing to RA economic growth, such as consumer spending, investment, and trade. Examining the linkages and dynamics between economic growth and budget spending is important for policy makers for future policy development as well as effective post-crisis response.

Literature review

There are many definitions and perceptions of economic growth, but the simplest definition is that economic growth is the increase in real GDP over a certain period of time with the expansion of the country's production capabilities and full employment of the population. There are various theories and models examining economic growth from different perspectives, and the economic community is constantly debating the functions of the state and the extent of its participation in economic relations. Thus, some emphasize the role of the state in ensuring economic growth, while the other opposes this theory. A rather in-depth study of economic growth and the influence of public expenditure on it was carried out by IMF researchers, according to which: public expenditure is the most powerful instrument at the hands of governments to achieve their objectives of economic development and social welfare, while emphasizing the importance of the size and structure of public expenditure [1, p. 56-57]. The impact of the growth and structure of public expenditure on economic growth can have various consequences: "at a low level, the productive effects of public spending are likely to exceed the social costs of raising funds. However, government expenditure and the required taxes may reach levels where the negative effects on efficiency and hence growth starts dominating. These negative effects may be more evident where the financing relies heavily on more "distortionary" taxes (e.g. direct taxes) and where public expenditure focuses on "unproductive" activities" [2, p. 18]. Government can seek to create the optimum condition for economic growth, and so far as they fail to do so, growth will be impeded. But it is also true that active government intervention can, in some cases, retard rather than help growth [3, p. 18]. Dao Minh Quang discussing the impact of government spending on economic growth, notes that, government need to devise programs aimed at increasing investment in physical capital relative to total output in order to promote greater economic per capita, at the same time governments in developing countries need to continue policies designed to increase the value added per work to encourage further growth. A policy implication is for governments in developing countries to undertake measure to combine capital, labour and skills more efficiently, while applying new knowledge [4, p. 84-85]. It is obvious that the mechanisms of promoting economic growth of public expenditures are different depending on the direction of public expenditures. For example, Bose et al. found that government capital expenditures have a positive and significant relationship with economic growth; moreover, at the disaggregated level, government investment in education and total education spending were the only

expenditures that had a positive effect on economic growth, despite for budget constraints and after accounting for unobserved variables [5, p. 549]. Ghosh and Gregoriou also found a link between disaggregated public expenditure and economic growth, with operating and maintenance spending having a greater impact on economic growth than spending on education and health [6, p. 86]. According to Nobel laureate Paul Romer, economic growth is the result of endogenous factors and the endogenous growth theory explains the new concept of human capital, skills (specialization), and knowledge productivity growth [7, p. 76] Romer's studies were further developed by Lucas. The main difference between Romer's and Lucas's studies is that according to Romer, endogenous growth in the economy is driven by accumulated technology (or knowledge), thereby establishing a link between human capital and economic growth, where human capital is seen as "knowledge" and "idea" ", then in Lucas's theory it is human capital by itself that has non-diminishing marginal returns and creates endogenous growth [8, p. 154].

Thus, according to Chapanyan, "as a result of studying about fifteen models, it turned out that there is a strong relationship between the components of public expenditures and economic growth, at the same time, productive expenditures have a positive impact on economic growth, and non-productive expenditures have a negative impact" [9, p. 87].

Macroeconomic environment is very crucial for the effectiveness of macroeconomic policy, however, being small and open, Armenian economy is always under influence of both economic and other type of risks transferred from the external environment [10, p. 3], and from the policymakers' point of view for each country separate analysis should be done, to have idea about the most expected impact of public investment on macroeconomic variables [11, p. 46].

According to Sandoyan, "The economic growth factors changed during different periods in Armenia. After the first economic crisis, construction became the main driver of economic development until the global financial crisis, forming new economic drivers. In the current economic structure, services remained the main development driver, along with industry and agriculture becoming the other driving forces, increasing the export potential of the economy" [10, p.44-59].

Methodological Approach

Taking into account the purpose of the article, a study and analysis of the literature on economic growth and its structure was carried out first. With the aim of understanding the characteristics of the formation of economic growth, as well as to reveal the relationship between economic growth and government spending, databases were used to make comparisons between the indicators of RA and other countries. During the research, we mainly used the methods of statistical, comparative studies, general scientific analysis, groupings, and generalizations. During the research we calculate correlation between economic growth and contribution of expenditure in GDP growth.

Statistical databases regularly published by international organizations (World Bank, OECD, etc.), as

well as official data published by the Statistical Committee of the Republic of Armenia, the Central Bank of the Republic of Armenia and the Ministry of Finance of the Republic of Armenia were used as sources of statistical data and chronological series necessary for the research.

Conducting research and results

Both in 2022 and in the first half of 2023, RA stands out with quite high economic growth indicators. Although the Ministry of Finance of the Republic of Armenia has set a target for the economy of the Republic of Armenia in 2022 7% economic growth, it actually amounted to 12.6% [11]. At first glance, such high economic growth can be considered an achievement, but when talking about economic growth, attention should be focused not only on its quantitative side, but also on its qualitative side, so the key goal should be not only ensuring high indicators of economic growth but also “the quality of economic growth” and sustainability, which depends on the underlying factors of growth.

The study of the twenty-year dynamics of RA economic growth (Graph 2) shows that the highest economic growth was recorded in 2003 making 14%, and

the deepest economic decline was recorded in 2009 - 14.1%. Thus, economic growth in RA in 2001-2008. had a fairly high rate during the period, when the average annual rate of real growth was 11.9%, but such economic growth was mainly due to the high growth of construction, which in turn was the result of foreign remittances. Later, as a result of the global financial and economic crisis, in 2009 recorded a 14.1% economic decline, which was a direct result of the decline in foreign remittances and the consequent decline in the construction sector amid the global financial and economic crisis.

2010-2016 the rate of economic growth slowed down to an average of 4.5%. The growth rate slightly accelerated in 2017-2019, making an average of 6.8%, which is mainly due to the growth of services, in particular, gaming services. In 2020, as a result of the COVID 19 pandemic and the Artsakh war, the economic decline of RA amounted to 7.2%, then in 2021-2022, high economic growth was recorded, which is due to the presence of capital and tourist flows, a positive shock for the RA economy against the background of the Russian-Ukrainian conflict.

Graph 2. RA real GDP dynamics for 2000-2022

Source: Statistical Committee of the RA, Finance statistics of Armenia, 2000-2023 (<https://armstat.am/am/?nid=82&year=2022>)

It is obvious from the Graph 3 presented below that the economic decline of RA is quite higher than the indicators of the countries mentioned below, for example, compared to the neighboring countries, Georgia and Azerbaijan, the economic decline of Armenia is deeper by 0.6 and 3.1 percentage points, respectively, and is inferior only to Great Britain, Italy, and France

among the G7 countries. At the same time, in 2022, in terms of economic growth, RA is the leader compared to the countries, a relatively large economic growth was recorded in Georgia, the growth of which is partly due to the positive shock caused by the Russian-Ukrainian conflict.

Graph 3. Economic growth in RA and other countries in 2020 and 2022

Source: World Bank, OECD, and Statistical Committee

From the study of the dynamics of economic growth of RA, it can be concluded that it is sensitive to external factors, which are reflected both in periods of economic growth and recession. At the same time, in

order to draw conclusions about the stability and quality of RA's economic growth, it is necessary to conduct a study of its structure.

Graph 4. The dynamics of the RA GDP structure in 2000-2022

Source: Statistical Committee of the RA, Finance statistics of Armenia, 2000-2023 (<https://armstat.am/am/?nid=82&year=2022>)

According to the main expenditure components, the final consumption has the largest share in the RA GDP, which on average was 92.4%. It had the largest share in the GDP in the period of 2000-2002., 2011-2014 and 2019, and the lowest indicator was recorded in 2007-2008 and 2022, moreover, household consumption records the same movement as the final consumption and the consumption of state institutions records a certain increase in the post-crisis period (2009-

2011, 2016 and 2020-2021), which is due to fiscal policy aimed at solving socio-economic problems.

Since 2000, investments in RA GDP have been growing in 2008 peaked at 40.9% of GDP, then it decreased smoothly until 2018, 2018 making 22.4% of GDP, and in 2021 21.2%, moreover, the investment of fixed assets has a large share in investments.

The balance of export and import of goods and services in the RA GDP is negative, it recorded a minimum index in 2021-2022. making respectively -7.9 and -2.8% and 2016 showed the lowest index from the previous periods. making -8.6%, it is noteworthy that such an indicator is recorded in the conditions of export growth, and from the study of the export structure. In 2022, the biggest contribution to the economic growth of 12.6% was provided by exports, about 19.3%, 6.7% was the contribution of final consumption, only 1.48% was the contribution of investments, and the contribution of imports is negative, that is, it does not stimulate economic growth. It is an obvious fact that the implementation of investments is a necessary condition for ensuring economic growth, but investments occupy a small specific weight in the structure of the economic growth of RA, and at the same time, the extent of its contribution to economic growth is also small. Moreover, in 2022 and 2021, in the conditions of high economic growth, the contribution of investments has decreased, which means that GDP grows only at the expense of consumption, and predicting high economic growth in the future can be worrying.

When studying economic growth from the demand side, it is necessary to pay more attention to

budget expenditures, because this is the main tool by which the state intervenes in economic growth, trying to stimulate it. 2000-2022 the average growth of RA budget expenditures was greater compared to the average GDP growth. It is noteworthy that RA economic growth is significantly correlated with budget expenditures. The relationship between budget expenditures and economic growth is not one-way: on the one hand, high economic growth contributes to the increase of incomes and therefore to the increase of budget expenditures, and on the other hand, the increase of budget expenditures contributes to the growth of domestic demand, which in turn contributes to economic growth. Graph 6 shows the relationship between these indicators, where it can be seen that in the years of high economic growth in RA, an increase in budget expenditures was also recorded. The share of budget expenditures in GDP in 2001-2022 was 24.2% on average. The Republic of Armenia significantly lags behind the world average indicators in terms of the share of public expenditure in GDP. For comparison, let's note that public expenditure in G7 countries exceeds 40% of GDP, and in France, this indicator is quite high, around 60%, in neighboring Azerbaijan and Georgia, this indicator is high compared to RA, which is around 31-32%.

Graph 5. Relationship between RA GDP and budget expenditures

Source: Statistical Committee of the RA, Finance statistics of Armenia, 2000-2022 (<https://armstat.am/am/?nid=82&year=2022>)

A sharp increase in budget expenditures is observed in 2008-2009. and 2020 while in the same period, there was a sharp decline in GDP, which is naturally logical: in the period of economic decline, the

state resorts to its fiscal instruments, stimulating domestic demand, which contributes to economic growth (see Graph 6).

		GDP		Budget expenditure
2001-2008	↓	11.9	↑	17.85
2009	↓	-14.1	↑	14.62
2010-2016	↓	4.5	↑	6.67
2017-2019	↑	6.8	↓	4.2
2020	↓	-7.2	↑	16.28
2021-2022	↓	9.2	↑	17.3

Graph 6. Average growth of RA GDP and budget expenditures, by periods

Source: Statistical Committee of the RA, Finance statistics of Armenia, 2000-2023 (<https://armstat.am/am/?nid=82&year=2022>)

Such dynamics of economic growth and growth rates of government spending can theoretically be interpreted as a natural and strictly regular phenomenon, which means that during the entire observed period, the "participation" of the state in the economy, in the form

of expenses, increased almost as much as the economic growth "allowed": in the form of taxes collected [12, p. 42]:

It is interesting to study economic growth according to branches, that is, the supply side.

Graph 7. The dynamics of the RA GDP structure

Source: Statistical Committee of the RA, Finance statistics of Armenia, 2000-2023 (<https://armstat.am/am/?nid=82&year=2022>)

It is obvious that the structure of the GDP has undergone significant changes over the past twenty years, so the share of services in the GDP recorded a constant growth trend and in 2022 making 55.5% of GDP. While the share of agriculture decreased to 10.4%, industry accounted for 18.4% of GDP, and construction for 6.8%. From the study of the structure of the GDP, it becomes clear that the "non-exportable" part of the economy has greatly increased, while the "exportable" part is still decreasing. Thus, 12.6% of economic growth was greatly contributed by services: 9.2%, industry: 22%, construction: 1.2%, and agriculture contribution: negative -0.1%.

Here, it is necessary to develop a policy for the promotion of the "exportable" sector, which will reduce the dependence of economic growth on external factors

and ensure more stable economic growth. In contrast to the growth of the "non-exportable" (services, construction) sector, which is positively influenced by the growth of foreign remittances, tourism, forms an increase in domestic demand for this sector, while the "exportable" sector (industry, agriculture) faces an increase in the exchange rate, as well as the problem of intermediate consumption inflation. Therefore, a certain change in the structure of economic growth is important here in order to effectively respond to negative shocks. To analyze and compare the contribution of public expenditure to GDP growth the, the trajectory of their respective contribution in GDP over the last 20 years is presented. For this investigation nominal GDP and total public expenditure were used.

Graph 8. Contribution of public expenditure to GDP growth, 2001-2022

Source: Statistical Committee of the RA, Finance statistics of Armenia, 2000-2023 (<https://armstat.am/am/?nid=82&year=2022>)

As we can see, the amount of contribution to economic growth is not only not high (maximum 5.7%, 2007), but also highly fluctuating.

Moreover, neither the size of public expenditures, nor the rate of economic growth, nor the public expenditures/GDP ratio had a decisive impact on the dynamics of the indicator of the contribution of public expenditures to economic growth. 2008-2009 and 2020 during the crisis, when the share of public expenditure in GDP was 30% or more, state expenditure "contributed" to economic growth by around 3.3%, in the event that in order to cope with the crisis, the RA Government had developed and implemented a number of state support

programs for the economy. Therefore, a small indicator of public expenditure/GDP contributes to economic growth to a small extent, and in crisis situations, the increase in expenditure cannot stop the decline. This circumstance testifies to the significant inefficiency of the structure of state expenditures and spending directions, on the other hand, it is also due to the structure of the economy.

In order to get a complete picture of the impact of budget spending on economic growth, it is necessary to take into account the impact of spending on the other part of the equation, supply.

Graph 9. The structure of RA state budget expenditures in 2022.

Source: Ministry of Finance of RA (MoF) RA state budget implementation reports in 2022 (https://www.minfin.am/hy/page/petakan_byujei_hashvetvutyun/)

According to the functional classification of RA state budget expenditures, social protection has the largest share in the budget expenditures of 2022, about 8.9% of the GDP. The second largest share of spending direction is general public services, 5.5% of GDP, the next direction is defense, 4.8%. The sectors of education, health, and public order, and safety are almost equal, making up about 3% of the GDP, which essentially represents an investment in human capital, which is one of the main supply-creating factors of the GDP.

Conclusion

In the current conditions of globalization, on the one hand, the close interdependence of national economies with the world economy significantly increases the risks of bringing the economic system out of balance and we can see that economic growth in Armenia is sensitive to external factors, which is reflected in both periods of economic growth and recession. On the other hand, in order to identify the features of the economic growth of Armenia, the growth of Armenia cannot be considered stable in any of the 4 stages divided chronologically. From this point of view, the imperative of the time is the formation of an exportable economy, and therefore the development of sectors with export potential.

Although the Republic of Armenia significantly lags behind the world average indicators in terms of the share of public expenditures in GDP, these indicators are correlated, that is, they derive from each other. Therefore, a small public expenditure/GDP ratio contributes to economic growth to a small extent, and in crisis situations, when the economy is in decline, the increase in public expenditure cannot stop the decline. All this is due to the small share of productive and multi-purpose expenditures in the structure of public expenditures.

References

1. Zouhar, Y., Jellema, J., Lustig, N., & Moham. (2021). Public Expenditure and Inclusive Growth - A Survey. IMF working paper, pp. 56-57.
2. Scarpetta, Bassanini, & Stefano. (2001.). The driving forces of economic growth: panel data evidence for the OECD countries. OECD Economic Studies No. 33, p.18.
3. A. J. Arthur, Commonwealth Government Printer, & Canberra. (1964). The meaning and measurement of economic growth. Australia.
4. Minh Quang, D. (2014). Drivers of Economic Growth in Developing Countries. Studies in Economics and Econometrics 38(1):75-85, pp. 84-85.
5. Bose N., Haque M E., Osborn D.R., "Public expenditure and economic growth: A disaggregated analysis for developing countries." The Manchester School, 75 (5), 2007, p. 549.
6. Nyasha S., "The impact of public expenditure on economic growth: A review of international literature" Folia Oeconomica Stetinensia, Volume 19 (2019) Issue 2, p. 86.
7. Daniele Schilirò, "The Growth Conundrum: Paul Romer's Endogenous Growth", International Business Research; Vol. 12, No. 10; 2019, p. 76.
8. Bas van Leeuwen, "Is Lucas right? On the role of human capital in growth theory", human capital and economic growth, p. 154.
9. Chapanyan, T. (2021). Theoretical foundations of the relationship between the structure of public spending and economic growth. Public Administration, pp. 77-88.
10. Grigoryan, K., Petrosyan, G., Vardanyan, K., Avagyan, G., Petrosyan, A., External vulnerability assessment of Armenian economy, Slovak international scientific journal, VOL. 2, № 42, 2020, pp. 3-12, <http://sis-journal.com/wp-content/uploads/2020/07/Slovak-international-scientific-journal-%E2%84%9642-2020-VOL.2.pdf>
11. Grigoryan, K., Petrosyan, G., Vardanyan, K., Avagyan, G. (2021). Assessment of the effects of public investment on GDP growth: case of Armenia. Sciences of Europe, No. 78, Vol. 2, 2021, pages 46-49. DOI: 10.24412/3162-2364-2021-78-2-46-60, <https://www.europe-science.com/wp-content/uploads/2021/09/Sciences-of-Europe-No-78-2021-Vol.-2.pdf>
12. Sandoyanan, E., Egiazaryan, A., & Voskanyan, M. (2022). Main Drivers of Economic Growth in Armenia: Analysis and Evaluation. Finance: Theory and Practice. 2022;26(4):44-59. DOI: 10.26794/2587-5671-2022-26-4-44-59, pp. 44-59.
13. Ministry of Finance of RA, Macroeconomic developments and forecasts for 2023-2025, https://minfin.am/hy/page/2022_tvakan
14. Agadjanyan, H., Vardanyan, A., Mkrtchyan, T., Petrosyan, A., & Minasyan, H. (2014). Quality of economic growth. "Economist" Publishing House of the State University of Economics of Armenia, pp. 1-85.
15. Ministry of Finance of RA, Implementation reports of the RA state budget: 2020-2022, https://www.minfin.am/hy/page/petakan_byujei_hash_vetvutyun/
16. Statistical Committee of the RA, Finance statistics of Armenia, 2000-2023, <https://armstat.am/am/?nid=82&year=2022>